

Post-2002 Dead Sea Scrolls Fishy Fragments — or Forgeries?

On Provenance and Authenticity: Some Cases

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It is well known that not all the Dead Sea Scrolls fragments found in the 1950s were sold by the Bedouin to the Palestine Archeological Museum. There are many reports that even in the 1960s and later fragments were still in the possession of Kando, and of other Arabs to whom they were entrusted, either in Jordan/Israel, Lebanon, Switzerland, or Germany. In the 1950s fragments were also sold to individuals, and ended up in private or institutional collections. Some of those fragments sold to individuals have been known to scholarship for many decades, others only became known since the 1990s. In the known cases of collections of fragments sold in the 1950s it concerns only one or a few fragments. Each of those collections has its own history and sometimes also different provenances. Often some of those details are unknown or unpublished. While several of those fragments from private collections were published in the 1990s, Dead Sea Scrolls scholars were amazed when after 2002 tens and tens of hitherto unknown and unreported fragments gradually turned up and were given and sold to private and institutional collectors. I recently published a list of 68 unprovenanced twenty-first century Dead Sea Scrolls-like (“A Provisional List of Unprovenanced, Twenty-First Century, Dead Sea Scrolls-like Fragments”; see my academia.edu page), but continuously reports of more unknown fragments are heard, so that the total sum may become much higher.

In 2005 Esther and Hanan Eshel published six of those post-2002 fragments (*Dead Sea Discoveries* 12, pp. 135-57). Scholars were most excited about a papyrus fragment with five lines containing part of 1 Enoch 8:4-9:3, and ignored the study of the other fragments. Hence, no one questioned the materially and palaeographically incorrect identification of the other fragments with existing Qum-

ran manuscripts, nor did anyone comment on the strange style of writing, with different styles of execution of the letters in one and the same manuscript. In August 2012, Torleif Elgvin, Esther Eshel, Årstein Justnes, Michael Langlois, and I revisited all the identifications made between the post-2002 fragments that were known to us and the published Qumran manuscripts. We concluded that none of those fragments could be identified as matching with a Qumran manuscript. We also observed that in many cases the writing on those fragment was executed differently from what we know from the vast majority of the Qumran manuscripts. I strongly contested the claims that these were Qumran fragments. I considered two possibilities. The first that these were fragments from one or more other findplaces, probably found after 1967. The second that at least some, but possibly many of those fragments were inauthentic, that is forgeries. This article will describe some problems of a few published and unpublished fragments. A few examples should suffice.

#1. The letters of the purported 4QGen^f (4Q6) fragment (Gen 33:19-34:2; item #54 in my “Provisional list”; image at end of this article) published by the Eshels in 2005 sometimes are similar to those of 4QGen^f, but in particular cases, they are written entirely differently. Compare, for example, the execution of *qoph*. More important, within the small fragment, the letters differ considerably. One may look, for example at the different (from angular to rounded) bodies of the *lamed*. Interestingly, Emanuel Tov (*Scribal Practices and Approaches*, 14) cautiously suggested that 4QGen^f could have been a scribal exercise written by an unskilled hand. The hand of 4QGen^f, however, is considerably more regular and skilled, for example with regard to the spacing in between words, than the completely unsteady hand of the new fragment. Also considered on itself, the execution of the writing on the new fragment betrays an inexperienced scribe. The size and the height of the letters differ more than one would wish, the spacing is imbalanced, and one cannot but be amazed at the forms of the letters at the beginning of lines 1-2 of the fragment: the strange *qoph* in line 1 (compare the entirely different *qoph* in line 3) and the vertical (in stead of diagonal) left leg of *aleph* in line 2.

#2. The two fragments which the Eshels incorrectly assigned to 4QIsa^b (items ##59 and 60 in my “Provisional List”) also have very strange letter forms. Again one may note the two rather different *qoph*s in the first line of the fragment of fig. 2b. But the entire fragment is replete with strange and partially inconsistent letter forms, which do not simply differ in morphological details. More importantly, the letter forms vary from crude to baroque, from angular to rounded. As an example of the crude, cf. the *gimel* in line 2 and the *aleph* in line 3. Unfortunately, the figure is of a bad quality and the skin seems damaged in places. The latter might also be the reason for the apparently too large space in between *resh* and *šade* of הָאֵרֶץ in line 3. The editors also refer to the shrinking of the material, which perhaps might explain the entirely irregular writing (both with regard to height and to stance) of the last letters in line 3, which are supposed to read עָלֵינוּ. One may note that here too, as in the Genesis fragment, word spacing is irregular, or, rather, often not present at all, resulting in a kind of irregular scriptio continua.

The two Isaiah fragments which were published by the Eshels were offered for sale in 2002 and for the first time sold in 2004. They eventually became part of the Ink and Blood collection, and seem to have been bought by the shady French Aristophil group, the entire collection of which was seized by the French Courts (in either late 2014 or in 2015). The much more interesting papyrus Enoch fragment from the same Eshel and Eshel article was bought by the Norwegian collector Schøyen (MS 4612/12). Recently (summer 2016), the collection of Dead Sea Scrolls and Artefacts from The Schøyen Collection was published under the title *Gleanings from the Caves* (ed. Torleif Elgvin; ass. eds. Kipp Davis and Michael Langlois; Bloomsbury, 2016). Remarkably, from this ambitious volume of more than 500 pages, the papyrus Enoch fragment (item # 19 from my “Provisional List”), as well as a few other fragments from the Schøyen collection (items ##2, 3, 4, 8, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20) are missing without further explanation. The absence of those nine (!) fragments from the volume is only mentioned in a footnote (p. 62), without any further explanation. After the first excitement surrounding those fragments published by the Eshels, this very first batch has largely fallen into oblivion.

I want to emphasize that none of the fragments published by the Eshels in 2005 can be connected materially to the approximately one thousand manuscripts from the Qumran caves. All the identifications given in that edition cannot survive a closer examination of the hand or the material. Statistically, this lack of correspondence, as well as the irregular writing would rather suggest a different provenance.

#3. The so-called Hargerizim fragment (item #26 in my “Provisional List”), because of the reading הרגרזים in Deut 27:4 with the Samaritan Pentateuch, rather than MT הר עיבל, has raised questions exactly because of this variant. I wish to point at other features. First, as in the other cases, this fragment does not match with any of the Qumran Deuteronomy or Reworked Pentateuch manuscripts (I also checked the hand of the Exodus manuscripts). Second, the writing of the fragment is, as Charlesworth himself already noted, very uneven, with the forms of the same letter varying considerable within the small fragment, and with forms of letters that belong to different periods. One could conclude that this is an unpracticed hand. In fact, a similar variety of letters, a few very similar to those from the הרגרזים fragment (compare e.g., the final *mem* of הרגרזים and שלום), are also seen in the Nehemiah fragment from the Schøyen collection, though some other letters are clearly written differently. (This Schøyen fragment MS 5426 — item #16 in my “Provisional List”) is yet another fragment that has not been included in the Schøyen volume). Thirdly, the remnants of the first letters in lines 1 and 4 are the *he* of the lengthened suffixed כמה and כה. These are quite common in many Qumran texts, but are with very few exceptions only found in texts that also have other lengthened forms and have a full spelling of the *o/u* sound. The fragment, however, has the normal defective spelling of לא (rather than לוּא) and the nonlengthened form העלית (rather than העליתה which one might expect). In short, the fragment displays many unexpected irregularities. This in itself says nothing about provenance, but it should serve as a red flag when considering its authenticity.

#4. A not yet formally published fragment is APU 3 containing Deut 8:2-5. The color photograph of the fragment has been accessible online for some time, and we discussed the fragment in Kristiansand in August 2012. The fragment has seven lines, of which lines 2-5 are of some substance. Line 3 preserves the entire line, running וירעיבך ויאכילך את המן אשר לא ידעת ולא ידעו אבותיך. Noteworthy in this fragment is the writing of line 2. The text in this line up to the tear in the skin seems to have been written with a pen with a thinner nib. Also, there was some kind of error in the writing of אשר. The *aleph* has been penned over another letter, and the *resh* has been partially written over the *shin*. As we have seen in many of the post-2002 fragments, there is a larger variety in the writing of individual letters than one is accustomed to. This is not merely a matter of variation which one might expect, but it includes very strange forms of some letters, such as the *mem* in למען in line 4. Also, some of the strokes seem to have been made in two moves, perhaps suggesting hesitation on the part of the scribe.

However, this fragment has another interesting feature. Its overall shape is somewhat comparable with that of 4Q30 frag. 5, which also has the entire line וירעיבך ויאכילך את המן אשר לא ידעת ולא ידעו אבותיך, both with the same three orthographical/morphological variants vis-à-vis the MT (also later, when reading שלמתך as against MT שמלתך, the two fragments agree). The line-by-line lay-out correspondence between the fragments extends over five lines, with the sole exception of פִּי at the beginning of line in APU 3, and to be constructed at the end of the previous line in Deut 8:2-5. A line-by-line correspondence could be expected if texts with the same amount of letters per line, but nonetheless never occurs over so many lines in the entire Dead Sea Scrolls corpus. The almost line-by-line agreement, as well as the agreement of the textual variants suggests the possibility of a direct relation between the fragments.

Palaeographically, 4Q30 (DJD 14:15: “a typical Hasmonean book hand, to be dated c. 150-100 BCE”) should be dated earlier than the mixed hand of APU 3. Rather, one might explore the possibility that APU 3 took 4Q30 frag. 5 as a model. This could explain in part the close line-by-line correspondence, be it that the different placement of פִּי rules out a slavish copying. The hypothesis of the scribe of APU copying 4Q30 frag. 5 might also explain some of the errors in APU 3. Thus, in

line 4 one would be inclined to simply transcribe **הוֹדִיעַד כִּי**, but the fragment actually seems to have written **הוֹדִיעַד בִּי**. The scribe apparently mistook the final *kaph* of the Vorlage as a *dalet*, and the following *kaph* as a *bet*. Similarly, in the previous line one could simply transcribe, on the basis of one's knowledge of the text **אֲשֶׁר לֹא יִדְעַת**, but in the hand of the scribe of APU 3 this reads clearly **אֲשֶׁר לֹא יִרְעַת**. In the latter case, especially if one consults the infrared black and white of DJD 14, plate 3, the *dalet* might be easily read as *resh*. To a lesser extent the reading **הוֹדִיעַד בִּי** could also have been triggered by less attentiveness to differences between the letters as they appear in the 4Q30 Plate.

Individually, each of these features might be explained otherwise. Line-by-line correspondence could be accidental, as would be proven by the small variation with the **פִּי**. Shared variants are possible. Variations, sometimes major ones, between two occurrences of one and the same letter exist with most scribes, and sometime we do find idiosyncratic forms. Occasionally a final *kaph* can appear like *dalet* (though in the line above they were very pronounced and also with another head bar). However, when those features accumulate, one might consider other options. In this case, I propose that a modern scribe with a fragment searched for an preserved and published fragment with a comparable shape as an exemplar to copy. The modern scribe would have used 4Q30 frag. 5 as published in DJD 14. He (or she) would have relied foremost on the plate and made some copying mistakes, but also on the transcription.

The assumption of a text copied on a damaged fragment might also explain some other features. The *aleph* at the end of line 4 after the gap seems much too high (which could be explained as a supralinear letter at the end of the line), and the *shin* of **שְׁלִמְתֶךָ**, which is written on a tear in the skin, has only been written partially.

The above are four examples of fishy fragments. But many of the other post-2002 fragments have similar features that raise serious concerns about provenance and authenticity. I and several colleagues have been voicing these concerns, first privately, and more recently gradually more publicly, over the past years. I do not suggest that all “post-2002” fragments are inauthentic. Some may be

authentic ones with a demonstrable history for the post-discovery period of the past sixty or so years. Rather, I expect that we might have a mix of some authentic fragments, probably from other find-places than Qumran, and many inauthentic ones.

Up to now owners and editors of collections of those fragments have demonstrated reluctance to consider and discuss openly the possibility of forgery. Palaeographical and philological study of photographs of fragments may raise questions, but rarely produce evidence that cannot be disputed. It is time for openness about the conclusions of the material analysis of those fragments.

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1. A Fragment of 4QGen^f

Figure 1. 4QGen^f

Eshel and Eshel, *DSD* 12, p. 135

Eshel and Eshel, *DSD* 12, p. 138

APU 3 Hargerizim fragment (downloaded from internet)

APU 3 downloaded from internet 2012

4Q30 frag. 5